

ENCODING-MAT: A Novel Encryption Method to Secure Information in Cloud Storage

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Abstract

Currently, the technological trend that plays a major role for the survival of any business organization is adopting cloud computing. Cloud computing offers dynamism, abstraction and resource sharing which may help an organization succeed in its business. All the resources are as cloud and it serves all over the world. Cloud services give many advantages to all types of business, both small scale and large scale industries. In cloud computing, management of data and services are carried out by the third parties and are not fully trust worthy, so there are many security challenges. The small communication devices like PDA, mobile, IPAD, etc. are widely used as communication devices by the poor and the rich people as well to access data from the cloud. Here, the challenge lies in security and device performance. Encryption methods are widely used techniques to solve the security issues. In this paper, a novel encryption method Encoding MAT is proposed. This paper elaborates on the working of Encoding MAT with the hidden private key and it is compared with that of the existing RSA algorithm.

Keywords: Cloud security, Encryption, Encoding MAT, Group mapping, Hash function.

1. Introduction

According to a recent Cloud Security Alliance Report, the biggest threat in cloud computing is its security. Therefore, Cloud Service providers must ensure that thorough background checks are conducted to access the servers. Additionally, data centers must be frequently monitored for suspicious activity. Data will be in motion in cloud computing and it may reside in on-premises physical servers, on-premises virtual machines, or off-premises virtual machines running on cloud computing resources. Due to the lack of security, several issues prevail in cloud. They are listed below:

- Data co-mingling.
- Privileged user abuse.
- Snapshots and backups.
- Data deletion.
- Data leakage.
- Geographic regulatory requirements.
- Cloud super-admins and many more.

Fortunately, experts agree that encryption is the unifying cloud security control allowing protect, control and comply [1].

In cloud computing, Data encryption for both data at rest and in motion should be a standard practice. Common encryption technologies are not always sufficient for keeping the data confidential in some organizations. Businesses are subjected to strict compliance regulations such as the Health Insurance, which require formal agreements between healthcare businesses and their partners who may be cloud providers. Hence, it is the need of the hour to ensure that all data sent to and stored in the cloud must be encrypted.

If data is encrypted while passing through the cloud, then the question who is responsible to control the security keys like encryption and decryption arises. Is it the customer or the cloud vendor? Most customers perhaps want their data to be encrypted to and fro across the Internet. It is most likely that they also want their data encrypted while it is at rest in the cloud vendor's storage pool. Cloud providers do not always offer security as a key feature. Cloud providers prefer that the customers have their own methods to secure their own data. Hence, the customer is required to control the encryption / decryption keys, and secure their data, as if the data were still resident in their own servers [2, 3].

2. Review of literature

2.1. Cloud Computing and its Security

Gartner [16] defines Cloud computing as massively scalable IT-enabled capabilities which are delivered as a service to external customers using internet technologies. Google's Google App Engine and Amazon's EC2 service are examples of Cloud computing. Cloud computing has unique attributes that require risk assessment in areas such as data integrity, recovery, and privacy. Gartner has also identified seven security issues that need to be addressed before enterprises consider switching to the cloud computing model.

According to Mather, Tim et al. [17], Cloud computing is a broad and diverse phenomenon. Much of its growth represents a transfer of traditional IT services to the new cloud model, but there is also scope for creation of substantial new businesses and revenue streams. Cloud computing offers the promise of more efficient and cost-effective computing to facilitate information use, but also expands known risks and introduces new risks yet to be discovered and managed.

Qian, Ling et al. [18] state that the cloud computing has been evolved from internal IT system to public service, from cost-saving tools to revenue generator, and from ISP to telecom. The authors have analyzed the concept, history, pros and cons of cloud computing as well as the value chain and standardization effort.

Zhao et al. [19], in their view, explain that cloud computing has numerous benefits for its users and at the same time, it raises some security problems which slow down its use. They have presented security issues for cloud models: IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS and pointed out that storage, virtualization, and networks are the biggest concerns in cloud computing.

In cloud security alliance[24], some useful technologies and best practices for securing data within various modules include Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a service (PaaS) and Software as a Service (SaaS). A survey by Cloud Security Alliance (CSA) and IEEE indicates that enterprises across sectors are eager to adopt cloud computing but that security is needed both to accelerate cloud adoption on a wide scale and to respond to regulatory drivers. It also details that cloud computing is shaping the future of IT but the absence of a compliance environment is having a deep impact on cloud computing growth.

The Cloud Computing Use Case Discussion [21] Group discusses the different Use Case scenarios and related requirements that may exist in the cloud model. They consider use cases from different perspectives including those of the customers, the developers and security the engineers.

ENISA[22] investigated the different security risks related to adopting cloud computing along with the affected assets, the risks likelihood impacts, and vulnerabilities in the cloud computing which may lead to such risks.

Dahbur et al. [23] describe the desirable benefits of cloud, risks and security concerns that must be considered and addressed correctly. They categorize many of the security issues introduced by the "cloud" survey the risks, threats and vulnerabilities, and make the necessary recommendations that can help to promote the benefits and mitigate the risks associated with cloud computing.

Sasirekha and Hemalatha [30, 31] observe that cryptographic techniques are found to be very efficient in dealing with a number of software threats and attacks. They have identified that code encryption has received much attention in the field of software security. Number theoretic and hadamard matrix methods have been used for transferring the code to the clients in a secured way.

According to Hashizume et al. [25], Cloud computing appears as distributed services with all resources as services and delivered over the internet. It enriches accessibility on demand in an efficient and more cost effective manner. Challenges in security leads to compliance, privacy and legal issues. There is an uncertainty of moving security applications as a cloud. This uncertainty has created great attraction for research on security in cloud computing. The cloud solution provider must ensure privacy and security control over their applications and data.

Garg et al. [26] in their vision, they propose to extend control measures from the enterprise to the cloud through the use of Trusted Computing and applied cryptographic techniques.

These measures should alleviate much of today's fear of cloud computing.

2.2. Security through cryptography

Juels and Kaliski [27] describe a proof of retrievability model. It ensures possession of data on archive service system by adding 'sentinels' blocks for detection purpose, and file encrypted to protect the special blocks.

According to Paul, A. J. et al. [28], substitution and diffusion operations, based on the matrix, facilitate fast conversion of plain text and images into cipher text and cipher images. They have proved that their algorithm is much faster than AES [28]. Paul, A. J. et al. [29] have developed an encryption algorithm with substitution mapping, translation and transposing operations. This has two advantages over traditional algorithms. They are simpler and much faster and highly secured.

Haitner et al. [32] proved that two-to-one hash function achieves better parameters compared with one-way hash function.

Ren et al. [33] proposed a dual protection with the DES algorithm and RSA algorithm securing data transmission in the Bluetooth system in an efficient manner.

Vellaikannan et al. [15] have proposed a novel method for sharing messages confidentially. This method is applicable to lengthy messages. Diagonal matrices induced from Quadratic forms are preferred for encoding as their inverses can be easily obtained. This technique provides a transaction of the least amount of messaging between the sender and the receiver. (It is sufficient to know the codes of use and the Quadratic form). Here the security is assured. Higher order diagonal matrices are preferred as their inverses can be easily found. When the size of the message is too large, new string operations may be defined and the message can be split for suitable process.

3. Cloud computing

Cloud computing is viewed as one of the most promising technologies in computing today, inherently able to address a number of issues. In the cloud deployment model networking, platform, storage and software infrastructure are provided as services with the aim of scale up or down depending on the demand as depicted in the fig 1. The three main deployment models are Private cloud, Public cloud and Hybrid cloud.

The private cloud is set up within an organization's internal enterprise data centre. In the private cloud, scalable resources and virtual applications provided by the cloud vendor are pooled together and available for cloud users to share and use, whereas in a Public cloud resources are dynamically provisioned on a fine-grained, self-service basis over the Internet. They are less secure than the other models. Hybrid cloud is a private cloud linked to one or more external cloud services, centrally managed, provisioned as a single unit, and circumscribed by a secure network [20]. The three main cloud service delivery models are: Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) and Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) [19, 20].

Fig 1: Cloud Deployment Model

3.1. Cloud Characteristics

The following are the number of key characteristics of cloud computing that have been identified [5, 6]:

Flexibility/Elasticity: Users can rapidly access computing resources, as required, without human interface. Capabilities can be rapidly and elastically provisioned, in some cases automatically, to quickly scale up or down.

Scalability of infrastructure: New nodes can be introduced or removed from the network with limited modifications in infrastructure and software. Cloud architecture can scale horizontally or vertically, according to the demand of the users.

Broad network access: Capabilities are available over the network and accessed via standard methodologies that promote use by heterogeneous platforms and networks (e. g., mobile phones, laptops, and PDAs).

Location independence: The customer has no control or knowledge over the exact location of the provided resources, but may be able to specify location at a higher level of abstraction (e. g., country, state, or data center).

Reliability: Provides the complete use of multiple redundant sites which makes cloud computing suitable for business continuity and disaster recovery.

Economies of scale and cost effectiveness: Irrelevant to the deployment model, cloud implementations can be as large as possible and it takes advantage of the economies of scale. Large deployments can often be located close to cheap power stations and in low priced real estate to lower costs.

Sustainability: This can be achieved by means of improved resource utilization, more efficient systems, and carbon neutrality.

Need for Security

Cloud implementations often contain advanced security technologies, mostly available due to the centralization of data

and universal architecture. The homogeneous resource pooled nature of the cloud enables cloud providers to focus all their security resources on securing the cloud architecture. At the same time, the automation capabilities within a cloud, combined with the large focused security resources, usually result in advanced security capabilities. Maintaining a perspicacious vision is essential in a field.

Cloud data encryption should be a standard practice when data is stored in the public cloud. Encryption should start at local servers and continue across the LAN and WAN for data in-flight and data at-rest in remote cloud storage.

Both a cloud provider and an user can supply encryption. So it is important to understand what the public cloud provider supplies and the gaps to be filled by excellent security. Provider-side encryption is convenient, but that means the provider has the keys to the sensitive data of the client. Therefore, cloud providers can surrender user data to government agencies without the user's knowledge or consent. To avoid potential provider abuses, businesses should use user-side encryption and key management.

Users should find the best encryption services for the specific cloud environment. There are numerous encryption products designed for private, public and hybrid cloud users.

Strong encryption and careful key management are essential elements of any cloud strategy. To address changes to legal, regulatory and threat assessments, cloud data should be reviewed regularly.

3.2. Cloud Security Measures

Cloud Computing is widely accepted by several organizations all over the world. Thus, there is a need to take various security measures to maintain data security in the cloud. A few of them are listed here [7, 8, 10, 11]:

- Choosing the best Cloud Security Provider (CSP) after a good survey and analysis is necessary.
- Transmission of data should be from a secure channel.
- Regular auditing of the security policies should be undertaken
- Data privacy should be maintained.
- Regular training programmes should be conducted to keep the skills of the security team updated.
- Updated policies, standards and guidelines should be followed by the provider and these standards should be regularly reviewed.
- Data encryption techniques should be used before data enters the cloud.
- Trust should be maintained between the provider and the cloud user by applying several security policies and process control techniques.
- Provisions for the regular back-up of data and recovery in case of server/system failure should be made.

4. RSA Algorithm

Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) algorithm is one of the popular and secure public-key encryption algorithmic methods. The algorithm is used to capitalize on the fact that there is no efficient way to factor very large numbers [12, 13].

Using an encryption key (e, n) , the algorithm can be explained in the following way:

1. Represent the message as an integer between 0 and $(n-1)$. Large messages can be broken up into a number of blocks. Each block would then be represented by an integer in the same range.
2. Encrypt the message by raising it to the e th power modulo n . The result is a ciphertext message C .
3. To decrypt ciphertext message C , raise it to another power d modulo n

The encryption key (e, n) is made public. The decryption key (d, n) is kept private by the user [12, 13].

4.1. Limitations Of RSA

RSA algorithm derives its security from the difficulty of factoring large integers. These are the products of two large prime numbers. Multiplying these two numbers is an easy task, but determining the original prime numbers from the total factoring is considered infeasible due to the time taken for their generation.

The public and the private key-generation algorithms are the most intricate part of RSA cryptography algorithm. Two large prime numbers, p and q , are generated using the Rabin-Miller primality test algorithm. A modulus n is calculated by multiplying p and q which are used by both the public and the private keys. This establishes a link between the private and the public keys.

The key length is expressed in terms of bits. The public key consists of the modulus n , and a public exponent, e , which is set at 65537, as it is a prime number that is not too large. The private key consists of the modulus n and the private exponent d , which is calculated using the Extended Euclidean algorithm [14].

5. Proposed Methodology

Plain text is available in an untruth server under cloud computing. Plain text is denoted as T which is divided into n blocks of equal lengths:

$T = t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n$, where $n = \lceil |t|/l \rceil$. Here l is the length of each file block. The proposed encryption methods are used to encrypt this file block into an unpredictable format. They are described below:

Get-Data(): For the text message, there is no change. For the mathematical figures and for the simple images read only the required points [pixels (x, y)]. These points will be converted into cipher text for security purpose and it will be decrypted and used with any one of draw functions which will draw the required figure at destination point.

Text-ascii(): Text message will be converted into a stream of numeric values $[N_1, N_2, N_3, \dots, N_n]$.

ENCODING-MAT: Numeric values formed as matrix elements V and multiplied with encoding matrix B [formed from existing matrix – hidden key] to form encryption matrix E .

Final-output(): For the plain text, output will be text message by decrypting numerical values in the final step. For mathematical figures and for the simple image, the decrypted points are used to draw the required image.

The main aim of using ENCODING MAT encryption techniques are to meet the challenges of small communication devices like mobile, PDA, etc. and to store data in cloud when data is in rest. The main advantage of using these techniques are that they are must faster than the other standard encryption techniques. This method is used to encrypt the given message in various formats quickly. ENCODING MAT is effectively used in symmetric cryptography. The following section describes the algorithm in detail:

Input to this encryption technique is text or number format. Input matrix is denoted as V .

$V = e_{ij} \ 1 < i < r ; 1 < j < c$ where r and c are rows and columns and e_{ij} is an element [ith row and jth column] in V matrix.

Encryption Process includes the following steps

- Convert text message into a stream of numerical values.
- Place the data into a matrix.
- Form encoding matrix using the number of columns of input matrix.
- Multiply the data by the encoding matrix.
- Convert the matrix into a stream of numerical values that contain the encrypted message.

Input data will be placed into matrix form. The size of the encoding matrix is 2×2 and it can be increased depending on the size of the input matrix. Always choose the size of encoding matrix as square. Since this matrix needs to be invertible, it must be square. If the input matrix ends with an odd number of elements then make it as an even number of elements to form the complete matrix. Fill the last spot with a space, if the number of elements is odd.

The invertible matrix is called the encryption matrix or the encoding matrix and denoted as matrix B . The number of column and rows are formed by the number of columns of the input matrix. Here this invertible matrix is the key. Form the key from the input matrix by reshuffling the elements by circularly shift right and put -ve sign for alternative elements, till the square matrix elements get filled.

$$B_{ij} = (-)^j (CSR) V_{kl}$$

where $1 < i <= c ; 1 < j <= c ; 1 < k <= r ; 1 < l <= c$

[if $(k=r$ and $l=c)$ then $(k=1$ and $l=1)$]

Where CSR – Circular Shift Right ; V -input matrix; B – encoding matrix with $c \times c$ size; i & j and k & l are indices.

B_{ij} formed from the existing matrix and this matrix can be inverted if and only if the determinant value is not equal to zero. CSR helps to find the next square matrix, if the current matrix is not an invertible matrix. Fig 2 and 3 shows the flow diagram for the encryption and decryption process for the encoding mat.

After arriving at the encoding matrix, multiply with input matrix to encrypt the elements, encrypted matrix denoted as E , $E = V \times B$

Convert the matrix E into a stream of numerical values that contain the encrypted message. Fig 4 clearly depicts the encryption and decryption process of the encoding MAT algorithm.

Fig 2: Flow diagram for Encryption Process

Fig 3: Flow diagram for Decryption Process

Algorithm for ENCODING – MAT:

Encryption Process:

- Step 1: Read the text message & Convert it into stream of numerical values.
- Step 2: Store data in matrix V.
- Step 3: Form encoding matrix B.
- Select the next cxc elements from V and form B.
- Step 4: If determinant value of B is equal to zero, then go to step 3.
- Step 5: Encrypted matrix $E = V \times B$

Decryption Process:

- Step 1: Read Encryption matrix E
- Step 2: Find the inverse of encoding matrix BI
- Step 3: Decrypted matrix $V = E \times BI$

Fig 4: Algorithm for Encoding MAT

6. Results And Discussion

When calculating power value it occupies more bits so maximum values handled by the existing method is less. Results of Table 1 and Fig. 4 show that the maximum values handled by ENCODING-MAT method with varying key sizes are commendable and this method handles more than 4 times of the existing ones. When the processor uses less bit size in small devices, then this method plays an important role in encryption method which can handle high maximum values when compared with RSA.

TABLE 1: Comparison of maximum values handled by RSA and ENCODING MAT

Key Size (in Bits)	Maximum Values handled by	
	RSA	ENCODING-MAT
8	16	128
16	32	256
32	64	512
64	128	1024
128	256	2048

Fig 4: Comparison chart for the range of values handled by RSA and ENCODING MAT

ENCODING-MAT encryption method is implemented and compared with the standard RSA algorithm. Comparison result is displayed on Table 2 and in Fig 5 result shows that the average performance of ENCODING-MAT work high when compared with the existing scheme. Initially, for less key size, the existing technique shows a higher performance than ENCODING-MAT but increase in key size, It proves that the ENCODING method gives a higher performance that is more than two times, when compared with the existing one due to its nature of power value calculation which is a time consuming operation.

TABLE 2: Comparison of Execution time of RSA and ENCODING MAT

Maximum Value	Execution Time (in Hundredth Second)	
	RSA	ENCODING-MAT
16	28	16
32	28	22
64	28	32
128	28	40
256	30	50

Fig 5: Comparison chart Execution time of RSA and ENCODING MAT

7. Conclusion And Future Work

The result shows that the ENDCODING-MAT encryption method increases the average performance by double time and the maximum values handled by this method are more than 4 times. When compared with RSA, small communication devices can use this method to achieve a high performance which is more secure. Similarly when data is in rest at the cloud environment, the service providers can use this method to maintain confidentiality at a cheaper rate. Future work may include implementation of ENCODING-MAT in cloud environment under Platform as a Service.

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